

The role of parents and communities in promoting entrepreneurial careers for vocational high school students

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ABSTRACT

An ironic situation has emerged where vocational school graduates, who are trained to be work-ready, have the highest unemployment rates. This study investigates the role of the community and students' parents in promoting entrepreneurial careers among vocational school students in Malang, Indonesia. Using a qualitative approach, the research was conducted at three vocational high schools through in-depth interviews, observations, and documentation. Data reliability was ensured through credibility measures such as triangulation, verifying sources, and enhancing reference materials' consistency and sufficiency. A multi-case design with constant comparative analysis was employed. The findings reveal several key roles of parents and communities in fostering entrepreneurship, namely: i) Entrepreneurship is taught theoretically and practically through business incubation, the Creative Entrepreneurship Program, and managing school business units; ii) Parents support entrepreneurship by purchasing students' products, stocking the school canteen, collaborating in product sales, and participating in brainstorming sessions; iii) Schools partner with local micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) and national and international companies to train students; and iv) The community and parents assist in marketing students' products, and some businesses related to the school's program serve as practice venues for students. This study contributes theoretically as a reference on the role of parents and the community in encouraging entrepreneurship in vocational schools. Practically, it serves as a guide for school administrators to involve parents and the community in school entrepreneurial activities.

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1. INTRODUCTION

A vocational high school is an educational establishment that provides specialized skills to individuals, equipping them with the necessary skills to enter the workforce and meet the requisite competences [1]. Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge that the employment prospects for vocational high school graduates in Indonesia are not uniformly favorable. Based on data provided by the Central Statistics Agency of the Republic of Indonesia (BPS RI), the unemployment rate in August 2022 stood at 5.86%, corresponding to a total of 8.42 million individuals. Paradoxically, upon deeper examination of the statistics, it is observed that graduates from vocational high schools, institutions specifically designed to

equip students with the necessary skills for employment, had the highest unemployment rate. There is a growing recognition among the general public about the significance of entrepreneurship. This trend is comprehensible as multiple research findings have indicated that entrepreneurship serves as a viable remedy for addressing the issue of unemployment [2], [3].

Vocational schools are anticipated to fulfill the role of national education by encompassing different aspects, including the promotion of entrepreneurship. The level of interest in entrepreneurship among young individuals in Indonesia remains very low, the aforementioned phenomenon has a discernible influence on the proportion of entrepreneurs in Indonesia, constituting a mere 1.65% of the overall population [1]. A significant factor in expediting a country's growth is the attainment of a minimum of 2% of the entire population engaging in entrepreneurial activities [4]. The prevalence of entrepreneurship in Malaysia, at 5%, surpasses that of Indonesia, as well as Singapore where the corresponding figure stands at 7.2% [1]. In order to mitigate the issue of unemployment, a potential approach is cultivating an inclination towards entrepreneurship, hence motivating students to pursue entrepreneurial vocations.

It is widely believed that entrepreneurship education can improve the economic and social welfare of a communities [5], [6]. This is because it prepares students to face the challenges of the modern economy by encouraging them to think creatively, independently and innovatively [7]. Several studies highlighted the need for educational implementation to include cultivating positive student entrepreneurial attitudes and acquiring the necessary skills [8], [9]. It is important for schools to provide students with real-world experience in business as part of their entrepreneurship education so that they can acquire the necessary attitudes, knowledge and abilities. However, the implementation of entrepreneurship education in schools still has many shortcomings, for example, learning objectives and content are still conceptual (not related to local needs and potential/industry advantages) [10], [11]. Teaching students the importance of independence in their personal growth and development requires an investment of time and energy on the part of the school and students, because schools cannot alone in organizing ideal entrepreneurship education, which in turn can increase student interest in a career as an entrepreneur [2], [12]. Research by Kirkley [13] showed that efforts to promote entrepreneurial careers to students require policy support from the government, institutional management, parents of students, to the community.

Studies related to the role of parents and communities in efforts to encourage career choices as entrepreneurs have been widely studied by researchers in various parts of the world, both developed and developing [2], [12], [14]. The entrepreneurial process theory put forward by Bygrave [15] states that an individual's interest in choosing a career as an entrepreneur is formed due to several critical factors, namely personal (aspects of personality), sociological (family relations), and environmental (relations with the environment). Efforts to create new entrepreneurs among vocational school graduates, namely by growing awareness and interest in entrepreneurship for vocational school graduates, because according to the theory of planned behavior (TPB) put forward by Ajzen [16] that entrepreneurial interest is the best predictor that influences entrepreneurial behavior, so when entrepreneurial interest is low, entrepreneurial behavior will be low, this means that entrepreneurs and new jobs will not be created.

Research by Adha *et al.* [17] stated that effective entrepreneurship education can foster interest in entrepreneurship and encourage students to choose careers as entrepreneurs, with self-efficacy as a mediating variable. Costa *et al.* [18] emphasized that entrepreneurial intention is important to encourage someone to choose a career as an entrepreneur. Owusu-Kwarteng [19] explained that communities also plays a role in one's success in professional achievement. The research was confirmed by Bloemen-Bekx *et al.* [20] which states the role of parents and communities can encourage student interest and choose a career as an entrepreneur. Researchers in Indonesia are also interested in studying this topic, given the importance of increasing the role of parents and communities in encouraging interest in entrepreneurship and promoting entrepreneurial careers [21], [22].

Although there have been many studies examining models that can be used to promote entrepreneurial careers, not much has examined the role of parents and communities in encouraging student interest in careers as entrepreneurs. For example research by Wijaya and Rinaldi [21] examined the variable family environment support as a variable that influences interest in entrepreneurship, but does not examine other variables. Further research conducted by Adha *et al.* [2] proposed a model for students in planning their careers as entrepreneurs in universities. Meanwhile, Rodriguez and Lieber [23] mentioned that educational institutions have a role in encouraging students to choose careers as entrepreneurs. This research aims to determine i) the implementation of entrepreneurship education in schools; ii) the role of parents in supporting entrepreneurship education in schools; iii) the role of the community in supporting entrepreneurship education in schools; and iv) the ideal form of involvement of parents and the community in entrepreneurship education activities in schools. This study tries to fill in the gaps in previous research, namely examining the role of the community and parents in promoting entrepreneurial careers for students using a qualitative approach, where the majority of previous studies used a quantitative approach.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The qualitative methodology with a multi case study approach was used for this study. There were 12 people who participated as informants in this study. This included three administrators, six teachers, and three members of school committees. According to Moser and Kortjens [24], the sample size in qualitative research is quite small, the selection of participants is based on the researcher's evaluation of which potential participants are most helpful and have the potential to provide the best and most in-depth information. However, in qualitative research characterized by a particular paradigm, basic guidelines regarding sample size have been given [25], at least one participant involved in each case.

This research was conducted at three vocational high schools, all of which were located in Malang City, East Java, Indonesia. In-depth interviews, observational studies, and documentation research are the methods that are utilized for the process of data collection. Interview guidelines refer to instruments that have been created and have been checked by members and experts. During this time, documentation studies were carried out in order to provide supporting evidence for the results of the interviews. In addition, observations were carried out in order to complement the data and test the validity of the findings by comparing partial interview results with the findings from the observations. This results in a more comprehensive collection of data being acquired. The researchers used three different methods to validate their findings. It is necessary to do source triangulation in order to ensure that the data collected from one source and another source are equivalent.

The present study employed constant comparative analysis for cross-case data analysis. The analysis undertaken in each of the three examples yielded preliminary conclusions, which were subsequently used to compare the data obtained from these situations. During the process of data verification, credibility is employed as a means of assessing the reliability and trustworthiness of the data. The process of assessing the reliability of data through credibility is accomplished by employing triangulation, verifying sources, enhancing the consistency and sufficiency of reference materials. Triangulation is done with utilizing many sources such as interviews and documentation studies, to enhance the findings validity and reliability. Regarding the verification of participants, researchers employed a method wherein the outcomes of the study were communicated to the pertinent individuals. In order to enhance the persistence of researchers and obtain more precise research outcomes, it is crucial to ensure the quality of data and effectively communicate the detailed findings of the research. Subsequently, the researchers employed the sufficiency of reference materials in order to substantiate the findings of this study, as it necessitated relevant theoretical support.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

The results of research at State Vocational High School 4 Malang, State Vocational High School 6 Malang, and Private Vocational High School 2 Muhammadiyah Malang, regarding the role of parents and the community in promoting entrepreneurial careers in schools yielded positive results. This means that the three schools have similarities in promoting entrepreneurial careers, especially with the existence of this independent learning policy, as can be seen in Figure 1. However, the role of parents and communities in each school is different. The differences are as in Table 1.

The research findings show that the implementation of entrepreneurship education at State Vocational High School 4 Malang, is implemented in the form of theory in classroom learning and practice with a greater proportion to practice through business incubation in schools. The implementation of entrepreneurship education at State Vocational High School 6 Malang is implemented both theoretically with classroom learning activities, and supported by the Creative Entrepreneurship Program as a place of practice for students to implement entrepreneurship theories that have been given in class. The implementation of entrepreneurship education activities at Private Vocational High School 2 Muhammadiyah Malang is carried out both through academic classroom learning and also practices that focus on services to equip students with entrepreneurial skills from a practical standpoint. Students are also involved in managing the school business unit, namely Smud Mart and school cafe.

State Vocational High School 4 Malang feels that the role of parents is quite positive in supporting the implementation of entrepreneurship education in schools, the role of parents in supporting entrepreneurship in schools is that parents support entrepreneurship education activities by buying the work of students during exhibition week open to the public or the community is held twice a semester. Meanwhile at State Vocational High School 6 Malang the school received full support from parents of students in developing entrepreneurship education in schools that focus on services such as IT services, electronic equipment services, AC services, and adapter products that save electricity use at home. Parents also feel satisfied while at school students have additional soft skills after participating in entrepreneurship education activities. Private Vocational High School 2 Muhammadiyah cooperates with students' parents to fill the

school canteen and also collaborates to sell products that students make at home in the form of dish soap, herbal drinks, and snacks at Smud Mart (School Business Unit) and also supplies to partner of Private Vocational High School 2 Muhammadiyah namely Royal ATK (one of the big stationery in Malang City). Besides that, intensive communication with parents of students is established actively, especially in brainstorming entrepreneurship education in schools.

The role of the community in supporting entrepreneurship education at State Vocational High School 4 Malang is by collaborating with local micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) to help students in entrepreneurship in the form of culinary businesses for snacks, fashion, and also batik typical of Malang City. Apart from that, advertising and also businesses related to digital printing are in accordance with the focus of State Vocational High School 4 Malang in the field of graphics. State Vocational High School 6 Malang seeks to collaborate with several national and international scale companies to train students by providing opportunities for students to take part in training programs within a certain period of time then students under the supervision of the school develop service-focused entrepreneurial business units services in the field of IT and electricity which are the focus of the school. Meanwhile, Private Vocational High School 2 Muhammadiyah focuses on training students in the field of marketing products that are being developed by the school. One of them is with Royal ATK Malang in developing dish soap products. In addition, other products developed by the school such as herbal beverage products.

The next research finding is the ideal form of parental and community involvement in entrepreneurship education activities in schools. According to the data obtained, State Vocational High School 4 Malang, the community and parents of students are trying to collaborate with schools in supporting the marketing of school entrepreneurship products. In contrast to State Vocational High School 6 Malang, which wants the parents of many students to use services developed by students at school. In addition, several parent's or community business that are linear with the school's entrepreneurship program are willing to become places of practice for students. At Private Vocational High School 2 Muhammadiyah, with good cooperation between parents and the community and the school in an effort to develop school business units that have been initiated so that they are even better and bigger than they are now.

Based on the findings from the three schools, there are differences in the roles of parents and communities in promoting entrepreneurial careers in schools. Different ways of implementation create uniqueness in each school. These three schools have different characteristics, as well as the different roles of parents and communities. The focus of the business being developed also differs according to the characteristics of each school.

Figure 1. The role of parents and communities in promoting entrepreneurial career

Table 1. Findings across cases of the role of parents and communities in promoting entrepreneurial career

No	Focus	State Vocational High School 4 Malang	State Vocational High School 6 Malang	Private Vocational High School 2 Muhammadiyah Malang
1	Implementation of entrepreneurship education in schools	Learning is implemented in the form of theory and practice with a greater proportion to practice through business incubation in schools.	The implementation of entrepreneurship education at schools is implemented both theoretically with learning activities in class but supported by the Creative Entrepreneurship Program as a place of practice for students to implement entrepreneurship theories that have been given in class.	The implementation of entrepreneurship education activities is carried out both through academic classroom learning and also practices that focus on services to equip students with entrepreneurial skills from a practical standpoint. Students are also involved in managing the school business unit, namely Smud Mart and school cafe.
2	The role of parents in supporting entrepreneurship in schools	<p>1. The school feels that the role of parents is quite positive in supporting the implementation of entrepreneurship education in schools.</p> <p>2. Parents support entrepreneurship education activities by buying students' work when exhibition fairs open to the public or the community are held twice a semester.</p>	<p>1. The school has full support from parents of students in developing entrepreneurship education in schools that focus on services such as IT services, electronic equipment services, AC services, and adapter products that save electricity use at home.</p> <p>2. Parents are satisfied with the entrepreneurship education implemented in schools because students have additional soft skills after participating in entrepreneurship education activities.</p>	<p>1. The school cooperates with parents to fill the school canteen and also collaborates to sell products that students make at home in the form of dish soap, herbal drinks and snacks at Smud Mart (School Business Unit) and also supplies to school partners namely Royal ATK.</p> <p>2. Communication with parents of students is established actively, especially in brainstorming entrepreneurship education in schools.</p>
3	The role of the community in supporting entrepreneurship education in schools	The school collaborates with local MSMEs to help students in entrepreneurship in the form of culinary businesses for snacks, fashion, and also batik typical of Malang City. Apart from that, advertising and also businesses related to digital printing are in accordance with the school's focus on graphics.	Collaborating with several national and international scale companies to train students by providing opportunities for students to take part in training programs within a certain period of time then students under the supervision of the school develop entrepreneurial business units that focus on services in the IT and electricity fields be the focus of the school.	Focusing on training students in the field of marketing existing products developed by the school. One of them is with Royal ATK Malang in developing dish soap products. In addition, other products developed by the school such as herbal beverage products.
4	The ideal form of parental and community involvement in entrepreneurship education activities in schools	Collaborate with schools in supporting the marketing of school entrepreneurship products	Many parents of students use services developed by students at school. Some parent's or community business that are linear with the school's entrepreneurship program are willing to become places of practice for students.	There is good cooperation between parents and schools in an effort to develop school business units that have been initiated so that they are even better and bigger than they are now.

3.2. Discussion

Schools should make efforts to use appropriate techniques in implementing entrepreneurship education in order to help students build independent character [8], [26]. The strategy in entrepreneurship education includes not only the teacher's approach in delivering material, but also the school's approach in delivering material and using infrastructure to support the implementation of entrepreneurship education, as well as by empowering parents and the community to encourage quality improvement in the implementation of entrepreneurship education in schools [27], [28]. The research findings show that the three schools studied basically implement entrepreneurship education in the form of learning and non-learning. However, there is a unique strategy for each school, for example at Vocational High School 4 Malang by giving a greater proportion to practice through business incubation at school. Meanwhile, State Vocational High School 6 Malang apart from implementing entrepreneurship learning in class, the school also made a Creative Entrepreneurship Program as a place for students to practice. At Private Vocational High School 2 Muhammadiyah by focusing on involving students in managing school business units. The various forms of entrepreneurship education that have been mentioned have an impact on improving students' entrepreneurial skills, by integrating entrepreneurial values and practices into learning and non-learning activities [29]–[31].

Various studies state that parents play a large role in pursuing the success of the school program [32], [33], including the implementation of entrepreneurship education [33], [34]. The form of the role of parents in promoting an entrepreneurial career is not only in material form but also in non-material form [35], schools should always strive to establish good cooperation with parents of students in order to optimize the formation of entrepreneurial character for students at school, which can later increase students' interest in a career as an entrepreneur [36], [37]. There are several differences in the role of parents in promoting entrepreneurial careers at schools, for example at Vocational High School 4 Malang, parents of students buy the work of students when an exhibition week which is open to the public is held by the school, which of course this will increase students' enthusiasm for entrepreneurial activities.

At State Vocational High School 6 Malang, even the role of students' parents also plays a role in developing entrepreneurship education in schools that focus on services such as IT services, electronic equipment services, AC services, and adapter products that save electricity use at home. Meanwhile, one of the unique things that happened at Private Vocational High School 2 Muhammadiyah was inviting parents of students to fill the school canteen and also working together to sell products that students made at home. This shows that the role of students' parents is not only to provide motivation to students when students are at home, furthermore parents can also play an active role at school in striving for the success of school programs.

In promoting entrepreneurship as a student's future career, of course, it is not only the task of the school and parents of students. Communities should also take a role in promoting entrepreneurial careers [38]. Various good examples have been drawn from the results of previous research; for example research by Ndou *et al.* [39], which states that the community plays an important role in shaping the entrepreneurial mindset of the younger generation. Additionally, the community should be able to support the implementation of school programs, one of which is in promoting student entrepreneurship careers [40]. The research findings show that the community has played a big role in implementing entrepreneurship education in schools, for example at State Vocational High School 4 Malang by collaborating with local MSMEs to help students in entrepreneurship, especially in the field of advertising and also businesses related to digital printing that are appropriate with a school focus in the field of graphics. State Vocational High School 6 Malang seeks to collaborate with several companies to train students within a certain period of time then students under the supervision of the school develop entrepreneurial business units that focus on services in the IT and electricity fields which are the school's focus. Meanwhile, Private Vocational High School 2 Muhammadiyah focuses on training students in the field of marketing products developed by the school. The findings of this study indicate that the role of the community in schools is not only in material form, but more importantly in providing guidance to students through various means such as mentoring and training which of course adds to students' experiences regarding entrepreneurial practices [41]–[43].

The ideal form of the role of parents and communities based on research findings also has its own uniqueness, for example State Vocational High School 4 Malang collaborates with the community and parents of students in supporting the marketing of school entrepreneurship products. In contrast to State Vocational High School 6 Malang, which wants many students' parents to use services at school, and if there are several efforts of parents and the community that are linear with the entrepreneurship program, the school is willing to become a place of practice for students. At Private Vocational High School 2 Muhammadiyah, by collaborating in an effort to develop school business units that have been initiated. With each role that is carried out well by the family or parents, school and community in education, which mutually reinforce and complement each other between the three centers, it will provide a great opportunity to increase student interest in a career as an entrepreneur [13], [40], [44].

4. CONCLUSION

Strategies in promoting entrepreneurial careers to students include not only the teacher's approach in delivering material in class, but also the school's approach in delivering material and using infrastructure to support the implementation of entrepreneurship education, as well as by empowering students' parents and the community in encouraging improvement in the quality of implementing entrepreneurship education at school. The results of research in the three schools that were the subject of the study, related to the role of parents and communities in promoting entrepreneurial careers at schools yielded positive results, meaning that schools, parents and the community played a role in encouraging students' interest in careers as entrepreneurs. The research findings show that the three schools studied basically implement entrepreneurship education in the form of learning and non-learning, by involving parents and the community in its implementation, the roles of parents and communities also vary according to the characteristics of the school, not only in material but also non-material forms.

This research also has limitations, for example, this research was only carried out in three schools with urban backgrounds, therefore future researchers can carry out similar research by taking research

subjects with rural backgrounds to enrich the results of this study. The next limitation is that this research was only carried out using a qualitative approach, without measuring the effectiveness and impact of the role played by parents and the community, further researchers can conduct research using a quantitative approach or mix method by measuring effectiveness and seeing whether there is a significant impact on the role of the community and parents in promoting entrepreneurial careers to students.

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